

Sign-Meet Virtual Meeting Platform with Sign Language Recognition

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DoI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15348353>

Abstract

Virtual meetings are a common mode of communication but are largely inaccessible for individuals with hearing and speech impairments. SIGN-MEET is an AI-powered platform integrating sign language recognition, speech-to-text, and avatar-based translation to enable inclusive real-time interaction. The system uses Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN) for gesture interpretation, Hidden Markov Models (HMM) for speech recognition, and animated avatars for visual sign output. This ensures that deaf, mute, and non-signing users can engage equally in virtual environments.

Keywords: Sign Language, Deep Learning, Temporal Convolutional Networks, Avatar, Speech Recognition.

1. Introduction

Sign language is a vital mode of communication for the deaf and mute community. Traditional virtual platforms fail to offer real-time sign language translation, creating a communication gap. This project introduces SIGN-MEET, a system that enables seamless interaction between signers and non-signers using AI. With the rise of deep learning models